

Religious Tolerance in Nigeria: A *Sine Qua Non* for National Integration and Development

Ogbeni Sylvester

Dept of Religious Studies, University of Ibadan

bomboysylvo@yahoo.com, christysylvester2018@gmail.com

Abstract

The frequency of religious unrest and tension in Nigeria is antithetical to her much-needed national peace, progress and development. Religious tolerance, which can spur peace building, socio-political and economic cohesion has eroded Nigerians for the past four decades. A situation that has promoted nepotism and divisive tendencies that is counter-productive to the unity of the nation. Religious inclusivism is therefore a necessary impetus for needed national integration that can snowball the country for the phase of robust national development, because a nation devoured of peaceful coexistence cannot maximize her socio-economic, political and scientific potentials. This portends danger to national development. The paper interrogates religious intolerance and argued that religious tolerance will consolidate national unity and peaceful coexistence in a hitherto divided Nigeria state. The scope of this work is the Nigeria social space, while the paper will hinge on historical analyses for its methodology. Findings show that religious intolerance is a cog in the wheel of Nigeria unity. The paper adopts Talcott Parsons functional prerequisites theory for its theoretical framework. The work recommends the promotion of peace through education and continuous religious dialogue.

Keywords: Religion, Tolerance, Secular state, *Sine qua non* and National integration

Introduction

Nigeria is a religiously diverse society. The religious influences of the Christian faithful in the south as well as Islam in the North have divided the most populated Black Country in the world along religious cleavages. Man is naturally religious, he is a product of a divine speck, and this propels him towards searching and making effort to connect to God, through different religious conviction. This accounts for the acceptance of different religion all over the world/country. This cemented the anthropological fact that, all human societies have one form of religion or another¹. However, this development created room for the multiplicity of religion in various countries around the globe. Hence, the competition among various religions to increase their numeracy and to occupy space, this tussle birthed mutual suspicion, distrust and religious intolerance.

This is a time reflection of the realities of Nigeria religious situation. Nigeria is a multi-ethnic state with a population estimate of 219,937,103 million as at 2022.² There are currently, more than 100million Christians in Nigeria today. The country is home to three dominant religions, these includes, African traditional religion, Christianity and Islam. Meanwhile there are many others whom spheres of influence are within a limited space and with a handful of members. Some of these are the Bahai faith, Hare Krishna movement, Grey Movement, Humanism Movement etc. These religious traditions find foothold in Nigeria, because it is a secular state. Individuals and families are at liberty to align to any religion that gives them and many others spiritual satisfaction.

Theoretical Framework

This paper adopts Talcott Parsons functional prerequisites theory, which mirror human society as a system that has four basic functional prerequisites that comprises adaptation, goal attainment, integration and pattern maintenance³. According to Parsons, there must be a solution to social problems, as the society depends on it for its survival, because the function of any part of the social system is understood as it contributes to measuring up with functional prerequisites. These solutions can be effectively deployed only if they are institutionalized, in the

process they will be able to mitigate socio-economic and political problems of the society. This off course is a necessity for the continuous survival of the society. It then means that solutions to social problems must be carefully organized into the fabric of the social order in a way that its structure will be sustained as long as the society remains in existence. The implication of this is that, the sustenance of the society depends largely on how the system controls the environments, set goals that direct social activities, control and maintain a pattern of socially acceptable values that is institutionalized by the society.⁴ It therefore follows that concerned authorities should initiate and implement socio-political policies that will promote religious tolerance and discourage intolerance in the society. The paper posited that, religion and its social instrumentalities like love, peace, charity, harmonious coexistence and unity etc.

Clarification of Terms

Religion: It is the supernatural believe in God, as well as the development of relationship between man and God. After which man accepts His instruction as sacred. For Immanuel Kant, religion is the recognition of our duties as divine commands. It is unarguable that morality or ethnics is an important aspect of religion.⁵ In fact, some school of thought holds that morality evolved from religion.

Religious tolerance: It means the ability or tendencies to accommodate people and their religious traditions. Summarily, it is the acceptance of the opinion of people pertaining to their religion. This is a function of mutual love, understanding and respect.

Secular state: It is a state that is officially neutral in matters pertaining to religion. In Nigeria for instance, the 1999 Nigeria constitution states categorically, in section 10 that, the government of the federation or of a state shall not adopt any religion as state Religion.⁶ Despite this amiable constitutional provision, Nigerian is still experiencing a toxic reaction from religious intolerance. This is emitting negative vibes to her socio-political and economic development. Ordinarily, in secular state, state would not fund religious pilgrimages either to Jerusalem, Mecca or fund traditional rulers that promotes traditional institution, she would not treat citizens on religious sentimentality.⁷

Moreover, in a secular state, private matters such as religion, will be prevented from impacting public space. Religious symbols such as *hijab* and the crucifix cannot be worn by the citizens. Since all these are still evidenced in a purported secular state like Nigeria, it will be justifiable to assert that Nigeria is not a secular state in practice, but in reality, a multi-religious state. The practice of *sharia* legal system in some states in the North, with Zamfara blazing the trail is a credible testimony to this claim. This is so because, going by the provision of the constitution, the adoption of *sharia* law in some states in North, meant the existence of dual legal systems in those states, as well as the adoption of state religion, which is contrary to the provision of section 10 of the 1999 Nigerian Constitution.⁸ However, this move was promoted by the *sharia* debate in the constituent assembly between 1977-1978.

Sine-qua-non: Etymologically, it is a Latin word that means something that is essential to an individual, people or state, without which progress or goal cannot be attained,⁹ the implication is that, it is a necessity for improvement and progressive development.

National Integration: These two words have separate interpretation. A nation consists of people living in the same territory, speaks the same language, practice the same culture, share a common colonial history and similar characteristics.¹⁰ These yardsticks shows that Nigerian is a multi-nation state with a heterogeneous entity of over 250 indigenous ethnic groups. In fact, Nigeria consists of over 250 nations.¹¹ While integration means act or process of mixing people that were previously separated together.¹² The dividing factor in the context under review is religion.

Causes of Religious Intolerance in Nigeria

Religious intolerance is a blind, fixated mental psychological negative attitude, towards religious beliefs and practices that are contrary to another person's cherished beliefs and practices.¹³ simply put; it is an aggressive

tendency that an individual expresses against the adherents of other religious conviction. This could be triggered by the following:

1. Competition among Religious Bodies: The competition between Islam and Christianity has created a whole lot of conflicts among them. Thereby making religion a highly explosive phenomenon. In 2016, Governor Nasir El Rufai of Kaduna State banned Christians from public preaching. This act was perceived as a technique to diminish Christianity and a subtle way to Islamize the country, using the state as a spring board. The move attracted stiff resistance from many Christian bodies within and outside the country. In a related development, in 2020, Governor Nyesom Wike of Rivers State ordered the demolition of a mosque in the state, as expected there were reaction from Muslim bodies within and outside the country.

2. Ethnicity: It is obvious that Nigeria is a conglomeration of diverse ethnic nationalities; each region is dominated either by Islam or Christianity. The North is predominantly Muslims, while the South is dominated by Christians. The inability of one to tolerate the character traits of the other in their spheres of influence and dominance often leads to violence. For instance, in Adamawa state, College of Nursing and Midwifery suspended the admission it started, because some Muslims students in the state protested against the payment of parts of their fees to micro finance banks owned by a Church.¹⁵ Also, one, one of the strongest points against the current resistance against the Muslim-Muslim APC presidential candidacy is a continuous mutual suspicion/distrust that has engulfed Muslim Christian relationship.

3. Religion in politics: Nigeria political vibes hinges on the spring board of religion, there will be continuous national tension, since political influence is laced around religion and ethnic colorations. Thus, in our pre-independent political history, we had the Northern People's Congress (NPC) formed by Northern educated elites in 1940. The National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroun (NCNC), formed by Herbert Macaulay and Nnamdi Azikiwe, which eventually snowball from a national to an Eastern Nigeria political party. In the West, there was Action Group that was birthed by Egbe Omo Oduduwa.¹⁶ Moreover, political gladiators, often want to use the churches and mosques as a platform for campaign in the build up to any general election in the country. These have always been the case since independence.

4. The formation of political parties along regional and ethnic conclaves: This often leads to heightened tension in Nigeria. A practical mixture of religion and politics was observed in 1979, when the federal government led National Party of Nigeria (NPN) attempted to take over Kano state that was headed by Peoples Redemption Party (PRP). The federal government deployed unorthodox means to portray the PRP government as incompetent and weak, as well as created credibility problems for it, Mohammad Marwa's group was used, he perfectly fitted into the plans of NPN and enjoyed heavy patronage from the NPN led Federal Government. Beyond the initial reluctance of the Federal police force to check the heinous activities of Marwa's group. Politics played with the inquiry into the Maitatsine crisis in Kano that was championed by Mohammad Marwa, this marred the credibility of the commission of inquiry set up by the government.¹⁷ Again, in the first republic, Action Group (AG) was seen as a Yoruba party, Northern People's Congress (NPC) was viewed as a party for the Northerners, while the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroun (NCNC) was regarded as a party for the Igbos. In Nigeria today, it is only the People's Democratic Party (PDP), the All Progressive Congress (APC) and Peter Obi led Labour Party (LP), that have a national spectrum, others are tied to one ethnic group or the other.

5. Weak judiciary and complacent law enforcement agencies: The Nigeria Judiciary is weak and easily manipulated; it is characterized with the "black market judgment syndrome" and the 'Nigeria Factor' which implies that justice is always sold to the highest bidder. This is worsened by a booth licking Law enforcement agencies that has been bought over by the bourgeoisie and political class. These compromising stance of those that are saddled with the adjudication and enforcement of the law of the country, contributed to the continuous promotion of impunity in Nigeria, hence, those that are engaged in the act of murder under the cloak of religion are left off the hook and those that carry out the gruesome act will see it as "doing the work of Allah or God" This must not be allowed to continue in this country, for instance, Deborah Yakubu, home Economics Sophomore at Shehu *Shagari* College of Education Sokoto, was gruesomely murdered for blasphemy because she responded to

a WhatsApp post from a fellowship group through voice note. This did not go down well with her fellow Muslim students. Thus, she was lynched, stoned and burnt to death, for allegedly blaspheming Prophet Mohammed.¹⁸

6. The sharia law and blaspheming; Blasphemy means to speak irreverently of *Allah*, which means to speak against God or a sacred being. It is an offence under Islamic *Sharia* law which is enforced in twelve Northern states in Nigeria. These includes, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Niger, Sokoto, Yobe and Zamfara state. These laws negate the provision of sections 38 and 39 of Nigeria constitution, that guarantee freedom of thoughts, conscience, religion and expression.¹⁹ worthy of note is that section 204 of Nigeria criminal code, placed a two-year jail term for public insult on religion. Dramatically, accusations that are related to blasphemy are often leveled on Christians by Muslims or by Muslims on their fellow Muslim.

Several blasphemous allegations have resulted in the following:

In December, 1994, police authority in Kano took Akaluka Gideon, an Igbo trader into custody to protect him from aggrieved mob that were after his life. The mob overpowered the police, murdered him and gleefully paraded his decapitated head around the city of Kano. His offence was that his wife allegedly used pages of the Quran as toilet paper for her baby.²⁰ In 2002 an average of about 200 people were killed in a wide spread religion riot sparked by the Jovial comment of Miss Isioma Daniel, a London based reporter for This Day newspaper, who said Prophet Muhammad would have chosen a bride from the pageant scheduled to hold in the city of Abuja Nigeria. For this simply statement, the Newspaper office in Kaduna was destroyed by arsonist. The situation was worsened when the government of Zamfara state, issued a *Fatwa* on Miss Isioma, which is a call by Islamic community (*Ummah*) imploring Muslims to kill the reporter where ever they see him/her. All Muslims are duty bound to obey this command, which is regarded as a religious duty. She was eventually smuggled out of Nigeria to London.²¹

In March 2007, a school teacher in Gandu a town in Gombe a state in Northern Nigeria, named *Christiana Oluwatoyin Oluwaseun* was falsely accused of tearing the Quran. She was beaten and stabbed to death. The sixteen arrested suspects in connection with the killings were later set free without charges. In June, 2015, nine people (eight men and one woman) were sentence to death by an Islamic court in Kano. Their offence was blasphemous utterances against Islam. It happened at a religious gathering organized in the honor of Shiek Ibrahim Naisse founder of the *Tijaniyah* Islamic order, where the eight persons were accused to have said “Nassie was bigger than Prophet Mohammad”.²²

In March 2021, a water vendor (*Talle mia Ruwa*) was smuggled from a police station in *sade* a village in Bauchi State, was eventually beaten to death by a mob who accused him of allegedly insulted Prophet Muhammad.²³

In August 2020, a gospel musician, *Yahya Sharif Aminu*, was sentence to death by hanging for blasphemy, he was accused of violating section 382(B) of Kano State *Sharia* penal code. In a similar development *Mubarak Bala*, a thirty-seven-year-old president of humanist Association of Nigeria, was sentence to 24yrs imprisonment after pleading guilty to eighteen count charges of blasphemy leveled against Islam.²⁴ Again in 2022, a 30 years old market vigilante at *Lugbe* in Abuja, named *Ahmad Usman* was murdered by religious fanatics for alleged blasphemy. The killers masqueraded themselves as defender of Islamic faith. They hit the victim with sticks and stoned him to death, when he became unconscious, they soaked his body with petrol and set him ablaze.²⁵

Painfully, it was reported that a *Sharia* court in Kano, sentence a Kano based Islamic cleric *Abduljabbar Nasiru Kabara* to death by hanging for blasphemy related offence. He was accused of claiming that some *Hadith* that are narrated by *Anas Ibn Malik*, *Bukhari* and some Muslims about prophet Mohammed are hoax, he rejects the *Hadith* on the strength of falsification of facts, a stance he could not prove before Islamic scholars from *Izala*, *Salafiyyah*, *Tijaniyyah* and *Qadiriyya* Islamic societies that leveled charges of blasphemy against the cleric. In the principle of fair hearing, the Kano state Government organized a debate on the request of *Abduljabbar* on the 10th of July 2021, for the cleric to prove his claims. The late Islamic *Sheikhs Mas'ud Mas'ud Hoto* represented the *Qadiriyya* sect, Dr *Rabi'u Muhammad Umar Rijiyar Lemu* represented *Salafiyyah* group, *Abubakar Mai*

Madatai represented the *Tijjaniyya* sect, while *Kabir Bashir Kofar Wambai* stood for the *Izala* sect. The debate was chaired by Prof *Salisu Shehu* from Bayero University Kano. The gathering was moderated by the Kano state commissioner for Religious Affairs. Unfortunately, *Abduljabbar* failed to prove his claims convincingly.²⁶ Thus, he was sentenced to death for blasphemy on the 15th of December 2022.

Notwithstanding, the murder of a person or group of persons on religious grounds, religious intolerance could also be expressed in physical fights/assaults, attacking adherents of other religion, denial of other religious groups of certain benefits or social services like providing land to build a Church, mutilation of the several books of other religion and using verbal insults at members of other religious conviction, denying people the right to be gainfully employed or promoted as a result of their affiliations to a religion, opposition to marriage proposal on religious grounds, the refusal to support a particular candidate in an election, because of his or her religion and unhealthy rivalry among religious groups or organization due to religious sentiment. All these accounts resulted from the fallout of religious intolerance that is hatched by indoctrination, which snowball into fanaticism, that is birthed by ignorance, misunderstanding and misapplication of the pivotal teachings and tenets of religion.

The Effects of Religious Intolerance in Nigeria

The Nigeria constitution makes provisions for a multi-religion state and the entrenchment of section 15 sub-sections 4 of the 1999 constitution as amended, clearly stated that loyalty to the federation should override regional or state loyalty.²⁶ However this constitutional provision of merits and fair play has been sacrificed at the altar of federal character and quota system. The consequences are the politicization of ethnicity. Nigeria today is swimming in the euphoria of tribalism. The divisive line has religious configuration because the northern part is dominated by Islam, while Christianity hold sway in the south. Thus, the use of religion to ventilate tribal/ethnic protest. Hence, the ethno-religious violence experienced in the country over the years, which is contrary to the pivotal role of religion as a unifying factor. Religious conflicts in Nigeria are as follows:

Religious riots that took place in Kano on the 18th- 24th December 1980 led by Maitatsine group, about 4,177 Muslims and Christian were killed. Private and public properties were destroyed. There was a religious riot in Maiduguri between 2ND--3RD October 1982. It was led by Maitatsine, law enforcement officers, Christians and indigenes were victims, about 450 persons were killed and churches were destroyed. Kaduna religious riot was as a result of the effects of Kanfanchan riots. It occurred from 8th-11th of March 1987. Churches and other private buildings were burnt. An estimate of about 200 persons was killed. Christians and law enforcement agents were victims.

There was a religious riot in Zaria on the 10th of March 1987, where 200 people were killed, Christians, non-indigenes and law enforcement agents were victims, churches, hotels and several buildings were destroyed. On the 1st of April 1991, Youths in Bauchi State launched a riot where, places of worship were destroyed over 100 persons were killed. Fundamentalist/Extremist Muslim groups launched a riot in Kano on the 14th of October 1991, about 500 persons were killed, and again churches, mosques and public properties were destroyed. There was a communal clash on the 6th of Feb, 15th to 17th of May 1997, in Zango-Kataf. Government sources put the casualties' figure at 300 while other sources like Red Cross recorded an estimated casualty figure of about 1000 victims; again Christians, Muslims, six policemen and two Inspectors lost their life.

In Kaduna State a religious riot occurred in Feb. 2000, it was prompted by *Sharia* controversy. 2000 persons lost their lives. Properties worth millions of Naira were lost; five Manufacturing companies were closed down. On the 8th-9th of September 2000, there was an ethnic religious riot in Jos, the Plateau state capital, lives and properties were lost, the government led by Chris Brown imposed a dusk to dawn curfew. Again, Muslim Youth rioted against the organization of a crusade in Ilorin in 2003. It resulted in the burning of several churches. On the 28th--29th of November 2008, there was another riot in Jos. Properties worth millions were destroyed, as usual the government imposed a dusk to dawn curfew.²⁷

The Promotion of Religious Tolerance in Nigeria

The Centre for Democracy and Development (CDD) based in Abuja asserted that an estimated 13,241 Nigerians lost their lives through extra judicial killings, between 2011 and 2021.²⁸ It frowns at the current system that allowed those that perpetrates impunity to go unpunished. This is perceived as a tactical encouragement of such heinous acts by state actors and actresses. This is presumed to be the case regarding the day light murder of Miss Yakubu Deborah in Sokoto state. It was a rude shock to many Nigerians, that there was a violent protest demanding the immediate release of the two suspects arrested in connection with her death, whereas the taking of the life of an individual is against the teachings of the Bible, Holy Quran, other sacred books and universal morality. The United States Commission on international religious freedom (USCIRF) declared unequivocally, that blasphemy laws that are promoted in core North Muslim states of Nigeria, are inconsistent with Universal human right. The government of the federal Republic of Nigeria must correct this ugly development through constitutional legal frame work/reform.

Since adherents of different religious convictions trade and buy in the same market, receive treatment in the same hospital, work in the same offices (Private and Government), their children attend the same school, use the same public transportation and so on. Concerted effort must be geared towards the promotion of cross-cultural awareness among citizens that are grossly divided along religious diversities, in the quest for national development and integration. Religious faithful should uphold the concept of the Universal Fatherhood of God and perceive God as a village or family head, who will not be happy to see his children fight and kill one another for his sake.²⁹

This paper advocates for national forgiveness. Adherents of various religions in Nigeria should forgive one another of the past and adhere strictly to the path of peace, that is charted and promoted by various religions in the country. Leaders of various religious convictions in Nigeria should work together and disassociate themselves from violence and injustice. This can be achieved through an intentional enlightenment of their followers. This will enable them to eschew the mixture of religious related issues with violence.

All tiers of government in Nigeria should be neutral on issues pertaining to religion, state actors and actresses must not promote a religion against the other. It is ethically wrong for any Government to promote a particular religion in a multi-religious state. The Government should rather protect the right of individuals to practice any religion of their choice. States actors and actresses must garner the political muscle to bring instigators and perpetrators of religious violence to justice. This can be achieved on the platform of absolute tolerance by way of neutrality. If this was the case of Sokoto state government, the killers of Deborah Yakubu will face the full wrath of the Law, the handlers of the case would have being more transparent, because right now, it appears as if the case is shrouded in high level secrecy.

Imperatively, Nigeria National Orientation Agency (NOA), should double effort on its sensitization of Nigerians, regarding religious tolerance. This can be achieved through the continuous education of the masses on the need to embrace and tolerate adherents of other religion and eschew violence under the cloak of religion. The Police and other Law enforcement agencies should be awake to their responsibility, which is the security of the lives and properties of Nigerians. They must bring perpetrators of jungle justice against vulnerable Nigerians to justice. This will definitely deter others with such intention and could mitigate such ugly development.

Nigeria Government should establish an interreligious commission across the thirty six state of the federation with headquarters at Abuja. This commission would be saddled with the responsibility of working out modalities that will help promote religious tolerance and values in the country. As well as regulate and monitor the activities of religious organization across the country.

Conclusion

The unity of Nigeria is not negotiable. Killings for God and attempt to destabilize the country is abominable and unpardonable by the same God and the entire humanity. No mortal deserves to die through jungle justice and brute force. The spate of religious intolerance is soaring in Nigeria, because perpetrators leverage on

the history of impunity, weak, diluted judicial process and a highly compromised policing system to continuously repeat the heinous acts. Moreover, all sacred books forbid it. Men of good conscience should enjoined adherents of all religion to show kindness to humanity rather than a flagrant disregard for the sanctity of life. It will not be a misguided statement to authoritatively assert that, some religious extremists are psychopaths who hide under the coverage of religion to subject defenseless Nigerians to grave inhumanity.

Above all, law enforcement agencies must be neutral, swift and proactive in the application of the law by arresting and making perpetrators of religious violence to face the full wrath of the law, just as personnel of Nigeria immigration service are expected to secure the country's porous borders effectively, to prevent the influx of fanatical element from neighboring countries like Niger, Cameroun, Chad and Benin Republic. To check those that come into the country, foreigners in Nigeria must be properly profiled. This will enable the authorities to keep track of foreigners in the country. Moreover, religious leaders should inculcate the concept of universal fatherhood of God and the universal brotherhood of man into their followers. This will enhance love and promote unity.

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